

Estimation of Peroxydisulphate Anion in Presence of Quaternary Ammonium Ions

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The iodometric method for the quantitative estimation of peroxydisulphate ion in presence of quaternary ammonium ions (Q^+) has been investigated. Q^+ ions interfere with the estimation and should therefore be removed quantitatively from the mixture before the iodometric method is adopted. Stoichiometric amount of $NaBPh_4$ has been used to remove Q^+ ions and the procedure is described in detail.

IN the course of our studies on phase transfer catalysis involving potassium peroxydisulphate catalyst and quaternary ammonium (Q^+) salts phase transfer agents, it became necessary to estimate the former in the presence of the latter. The iodometric method for the estimation of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ could not be used straightaway in the presence of Q^+ ions because of the precipitation of triiodide ions as insoluble QI_3 salts which react only sluggishly with thiosulphate anion. It was therefore necessary to remove Q^+ ions from the mixture before the iodometric estimation was applied. Q^+ ions form insoluble salts with large anions such as tetraphenyl boride (BPh_4^-), phosphomolybdate, phosphotungstate, cobaltthiocyanate, Reineckate, triiodide, perchlorate, picrate, etc. and in fact soluble salts comprising any of these anions provide reagents for the quantitative estimation of quaternary ammonium salts¹. These anions therefore could be used to remove Q^+ ions quantitatively from the mixture to be analysed in the present work. However, a few of them are also oxidising agents and cannot be used for the stated purpose. We selected sodium tetraphenyl boride in this work. After studying several aspects of the problem, we standardised the method which we wish to report in this paper.

Experimental

Potassium peroxydisulphate (E. Merck, G.R.) was recrystallised thrice before use. Sodium tetraphenyl boride (E. Merck, G.R.), tetrabutylammonium bromide (Bu_4NBr) (Aldrich) and other chemicals (A.R. grade) were used as received. Double-distilled water was boiled and cooled in an atmosphere of nitrogen and then used. $K_2S_2O_8$ solutions were freshly prepared when needed. Standard $NaBPh_4$ solution was prepared by dissolving the required amount of $NaBPh_4$ in distilled water to which $NaOH$ was added to bring the pH to 10. The solution was filtered through cotton wool and its strength checked by gravimetry². A buffer of

pH 10 was prepared² by mixing 0.2 M Na_2HPO_4 (100 ml) with 0.25 M Na_2PO_4 (6 ml). The bromophenol blue indicator solution was prepared by dissolving bromophenol blue (0.022 g) in absolute ethanol (10 ml).

Procedure: In general, our solutions to be titrated were around 10^{-2} M separately with respect to $K_2S_2O_8$ and Bu_4NBr . The stoichiometric amount of $NaBPh_4$ solution that would be needed to precipitate out the Bu_4N^+ ion (called boride demand) was determined volumetrically² using an aliquot. To another aliquot was added $NaBPh_4$ solution as determined from 'boride demand' titration in order to precipitate out Bu_4N^+ ions quantitatively. The solution was filtered into an iodine flask through a sintered Gooch (G-4) crucible provided with a long stem. The residue was washed with boiled-out distilled water (4×10 ml). To the combined filtrate and washings (total volume 70 ml), $NaHCO_3$ (3 g) was added followed by 10% H_2SO_4 (18 ml). A 5 M KI solution (20 ml) was then added to make the medium 1 M with respect to iodide ion³. The solution was set aside for 30 min in dark. It was then diluted with boiled-out distilled water (120 ml). The liberated iodine was titrated with standard sodium thiosulphate.

Results and Discussion

In the initial series of experiments we used excess of $NaBPh_4$ to precipitate out Q^+ ions and carried out the iodometric estimation of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ in the presence of the precipitated $QBPh_4$ and of the excess BPh_4^- ion. We found that under this condition peroxydisulphate was substantially underestimated. The next logical step was to use the stoichiometric amount of $NaBPh_4$ required to precipitate Q^+ ion present in the system. However, the estimation of peroxydisulphate in the solution without removing the precipitated $QBPh_4$ salts gave a low estimation of the peroxydisulphate. The degree of underestimation was of course somewhat less than that

experienced in the experiments using excess of BPh_4^- described above. Finally, only when did we use NaBPh_4 in stoichiometric quantity as determined by the titration of an aliquot portion (see experimental), removed the precipitated QBPh_4 salt by filtration and then determined the peroxydisulphate in the combined filtrate and washings, were we able to get quantitative results (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ IN ITS MIXTURE WITH Bu_4NBr

[Bu_4NBr] $\times 10^3 M$	[$\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$] $\times 10^3 M$		Estimated %
	Taken	Found	
0.000	0.997	0.997 \pm 0.005 ^a	100 \pm 0.5 ^a
0.389	0.665	0.666	100.15
0.509	0.493	0.494	99.00
0.611	0.399	0.396	99.25
0.679	0.332	0.328 \pm 0.002 ^b	98.80 \pm 0.60 ^b

^a Average of three analyses. ^b Average of two experiments.

The results may be explained in the following way. The reaction of peroxydisulphate ion with I^- is rather slow. In the iodometric method, this problem is overcome maintaining a strong acid concentration in the solution during the 30 min period allowed for iodine liberation and using a large I^- ion concentration^{3,4}. However, according to Kolthoff and Carr⁵, the liberation of iodine from the reaction of I^- with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ is not affected by H^+ . The reaction being the one involving two negatively charged ions

its rate increased when the ionic strength of the solution is increased (positive salt effect). When we used excess BPh_4^- ion to remove Q^+ , the $[\text{H}^+]$ of the medium was reduced because HBPh_4 is a weak acid. As a result, iodine liberation was incomplete and we ended up with gross underestimation of the peroxydisulphate. The low result may also be partly due

to carrying out iodine liberation in presence of the precipitated QBPh_4 salt. Because of the following equilibrium reaction, part of the I_3^- ion would be fixed as insoluble QI_3 which reacts sluggishly with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$.

where, the subscript S and L stands for the solid and liquid phases, respectively. This reaction explains why low result was obtained even when the stoichiometric amount of NaBPh_4 was used to precipitate Q^+ ions as QBPh_4 salt, but the iodometric estimation was carried out without removing the latter. It follows therefore that the iodometric method should be successful only in the absence of excess BPh_4^- ion and of the precipitated QBPh_4 salt. It should be mentioned here that in the titration meant for the determination of boride demand^{1,6-9} not only the Q^+ ion was titrated, a small part of the K^+ ion also was titrated being precipitated as KBPh_4 . This however, does not influence the subsequent determination of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ by the iodometric method.

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